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Reference of a selected paper	Bláha, J. et al. (2013) Can Natura 2000 mapping be used to zone the Šumava National Park? <i>European Journal of Environmental Sciences</i> , Vol. 3, No. 1, pp. 57–64
Title	Can NATURA 2000 mapping be used to zone the Šumava National Park?
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Abstract	The paper focuses on the question, if zonation of the Šumava National Park (ŠNP) can be done using NATURA 2000 pan-European landscape classification. The authors proposed new variant of division of using existing data made by the Nature Conservation Agency of the Czech Republic (NCA) and data of important bird areas, organized by the NCA and Czech Ornithological Society. The main method used is ArcGIS based spatial analysis of the geospatial data. The result is presented as a new classification map of the Šumava National Park, which was performed as an overlay combination of various vector thematic layers. The final map shows division of ŠNP in 3 zones: 1) the most precious; 2) moderate value; 3) the common, normal value.
Introduction	The ŠNP is important natural heritage both for Czech Republic and for the European Union. The ŠNP is a unique mosaic of landscape habitats of exceptional natural value and protected plants and species of high significance. But recently there were debates on the politician level about the nature conservation in the ŠNP with special attention on correct zoning of the ŠNP. The zonation of ŠNP has undergone significant changes since its establishment in 2005. Now it was necessary to re-arrange the zonation which would include new information on the land cover types and landscape changes.
Methods	The zonation was done in two steps using ArcGIS Toolbox, mapping and modeling techniques of spatial analysis: (step 1): Overlay and synthesis of individual vector layers and geospatial components. At this step, all components were analyzed separately to calculate total area (number of patches), level of fragmentation and the % of the ŠNP area that they cover. (step 2): Generalization of final output. During this step, authors performed overlay and intersection of all the components. The important part of this task included generalization of the mask, which was done using expert knowledge supported by topographical and forestry maps and aerial photographs.
Results	As a result, the authors proposed new and more corrected zoning of the ŠNP, which includes following zones: 1) Zone I, the most valuable and strictly protected part of the ŠNP; 2) Zone I, 42,9% of the total area; 3) Zone III – 4,9% of the total area
Discussion	The authors used four habitats protected in Šumava NP as basic components of the Zone I (the most strictly protected non-intervention zone in the ŠNP): 1) spruce forests; 2) beech forests; 3) raised bogs, springs, fens and transitional mires; 4) other valuable NATURA 2000 habitats.

Using information on their spatial distribution and data from previous mapping, the authors classified biotops and presented cartographic outputs for the new zonation:

Conclusion

- A new proposal for the zonation of the ŠNP was prepared by a scientific committee of authors and submitted to the Ministry of Environment.
- This proposal took into account the current condition of the landscapes of ŠNP, their dynamics and the effects of natural changes.
- A special emphasis was placed on the population dynamics and ecological requirements of the most important, core species.
- The strictly protected Zone I includes the most valuable parts of the most important habitats and locations where the most important species occur.
- Any further reduction in Zone I will seriously threaten the survival of important species and habitats in the ŠNP.
- The zonation presented by the authors is politically independent and unbiased, which defines the *optimum* size of the core zone of the ŠNP.
- The proposal is based on the available data from Natura 2000 habitats and species mapping from previous cartographic works.